

EDUCATION ON BREASTFEEDING TECHNIQUES TO IMPROVE POSTPARTUM MOTHER'S KNOWLEDGE ABOUT EXCLUSIVE BREAST MILK PROVIDING IN THE DELIVERY UNIT OF TANJUNGPANDAN HEALTH CENTER

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Abstract

Background: Breast milk is the best food for babies because it contains many substances and protective factors that are important for the growth and development of babies so that it can reduce infant morbidity and mortality. Breastfeeding that is not optimal causes hampered growth and development of the baby and is one of the factors that triggers stress in breastfeeding mothers. Many factors cause the failure of exclusive breast milk, one of which is the mother's knowledge of breastfeeding techniques.

Objective: To find out an overview of breastfeeding technique education to increase mothers' knowledge about exclusive breast milk

Method: The design of this scientific paper is descriptive using a case study approach (case study research). By sampling postpartum mothers aged 20 – 30 years in the first 24 hours after parturition. The intervention that will be carried out is to educate postpartum mothers about breastfeeding techniques to increase mothers' knowledge in providing exclusive breast milk.

Result: The nursing diagnosis of breastfeeding is ineffective a. w the mother and baby experience dissatisfaction or difficulty in the breastfeeding process p. b the baby is unable to latch onto the mother's breast. The results after education on breastfeeding techniques and exclusive breast milk education showed that the patient's level of knowledge regarding breastfeeding techniques and exclusive breastfeeding increased, namely: the baby's attachment to the mother increased, the mother's ability to position the baby correctly increased, the mother's breast emptiness after breastfeeding increased, and the baby's suction increased. Mother's knowledge of exclusive breast milk greatly increased with a final score of 26 out of 30.

Keywords: Breastfeeding Techniques, Exclusive Breast milk

1. INTRODUCTION

Lactation is the entire process of breastfeeding, from breast milk produced to the process of baby sucking and swallowing for at least 6 months of life and continued with accompanying foods until the age of 2 years. (Anitasari, 2020)¹ According to the WHO and UNICEF, optimum nutrition for newborn babies through a global strategy of exclusive breastfeeding for 6 months. Globally, the number of exclusively lactated babies has increased significantly, approximately

44% in the 0-6 months babies during the period 2015-2020 but has not met the target of 50% exclusive milk. (WHO, 2020)²

According to Basic Health Research (Riskesdas,2021), 52.5% – or only half of 2.3 million babies under the age of 6 months – are receiving exclusive breastfeeding in Indonesia, or a decline of 12% in 2019. The rate of early lactation initiation (ELI) also dropped from 58.2% in 2019 to 48.6% in 2021. (UNICEF, 2022)³ The causes of breastfeeding failure can be influenced by internal factors such as mother's knowledge, education, and work, as well as external factors, such as the cessation of the promotion of formula milk for babies, the lack of health resources to promote the breast-feeding habits of mothers, and a lack of targeted welfare programmes run by some governmental agencies in developing countries such as Indonesia. (Kuswanti, 2017)⁴

Problems that usually occur during the breastfeeding process include inappropriate breast-feeding position, swollen breasts, injury in the breast area, nipple pain or sprain in the mouth of the baby just sucking the nipple just doesn't reach the areola, the mother does not know how to remove the baby's nipple correctly, most mothers when they want to end the nursing process without inserting their thumbs into the child's mouth or not by pressing the baby's chin downwards, as well as the baby has previously used dot. (Arismawati, 2014)⁵ Breastfeeding from an early age has positive effects for both the mother and the baby. For infants, breastfeeding plays a crucial role in supporting growth, health, and survival because breast milk is rich in nutrients and antibodies. For mothers, breastfeeding can reduce postpartum bleeding. (Ministry of Health of the Republic of Indonesia, 2020)⁶ In addition to benefiting the baby, the breastfeeding process also has significant advantages for the mother after giving birth. The breastfeeding process can prevent postpartum bleeding due to uterine contractions stimulated by the hormone oxytocin, accelerate uterine involution, reduce the risk of anemia, lower the risk of ovarian and breast cancer, provide a sense of being needed, strengthen the emotional bond between a mother and her newborn, facilitate a return to pre-pregnancy weight, and serve as a temporary contraceptive method. (Astutik, 2014)⁷

There are still obstacles in the implementation of the exclusive breastfeeding program, including the mother's lack of knowledge about the techniques of lactation that will affect the breastfeeding. This is because the techniques are not applied properly and correctly, so it is the main cause of the failure of the breastfeeding program. (Rismayanti, 2021)⁸ Based on the description, the author is interested in conducting a case study on the education of breastfeeding techniques in postpartum mothers to enhance mother's knowledge of exclusive milk.

2. METHODOLOGY

The design of this scientific paper is descriptive using a case study research. By sampling postpartum mothers aged 20 – 30 years in the first 24 hours after parturition. The intervention that will be carried out is to educate postpartum mothers about breastfeeding techniques to increase mothers' knowledge in providing exclusive breast milk.

3. RESULTS

This case study was conducted from February to May 2024, with the data collection scheduled for March 11-16, 2024. During the data collection, the researcher conducted an assessment for one day, specifically on March 11, 2024. The study was conducted at the

Tanjung Pandan Community Health Center, specifically in the Delivery Unit of the Postnatal Room. The researchers conducted implementation and evaluation during three home visits.

3.1 Characteristics of the Respondent

The subject of this case study is a single postpartum mother, whether primipara or multipara. The inclusion and exclusion criteria required for this research are as follows: Inclusion Criteria; The client is a postpartum mother with a normal delivery within 24 hours after childbirth, the client is either a primipara or multipara, the client is willing to receive nursing care, the client is willing to provide exclusive breastfeeding for her baby, the client is aged 19-30 years. As for the Exclusion Criteria; Postpartum mothers who require care due to postpartum complications, mothers with newborns who need special care due to complications during childbirth that make breastfeeding impossible, and mothers with flat or inverted nipples.

The subject of this research is Mrs. I (G3P3A0), a 27-year-old female. The patient's last education was at a Vocational High School. The patient's address is on Air Ketekok Street, Tanjungpandan District. I entered the emergency room of the community health center on March 10, 2024, at 10:00 PM WIB. Medical record number 10-XX-X with a diagnosis of spontaneous postpartum. The person responsible for Mrs. I is Mr. A, 27 years old, who is Mrs. I's husband.

3.2 Assessment of the Respondent

The assessment was conducted on March 11, 2024, at 9:30 AM WIB in the maternity unit of the Tanjungpandan Community Health Center, where the patient complained of pain in the perineum. In the examination of the patient's medical history, the patient reported that before being taken to the hospital, they complained of cramping in the lower abdomen radiating to the back. A vital signs examination was conducted on the patient with the following results: blood pressure: 110/95 mmHg, pulse: 77 beats/minute, temperature: 36.9°C, respiratory rate: 20 breaths/minute, weight: 72 kg, and mid-upper arm circumference: 24.5 cm.

The results of the assessment of the patient's delivery history indicate that the patient's last menstrual period (LMP) was on June 23, 2022, and the estimated delivery date was March 30, 2023, with a gestational age of 37 weeks. The patient's delivery occurred on March 11, 2023, at 2:00 AM WIB, resulting in the birth of a baby boy. At the time after the baby's delivery, the patient underwent Early Initiation of Breastfeeding (EIB). The type of delivery for the patient is a normal delivery assisted by a community health center midwife. The baby was born weighing 3.5 kg and measuring 48 cm in length.

The patient gave birth to her third child at 37 weeks of pregnancy. The age gap between the patient's current pregnancy and the previous child is about two and a half years. The patient provided exclusive breastfeeding starting from her first child, but it was only given until the baby was eight months old because the patient became pregnant with her second child. For the second child, the patient provided exclusive breastfeeding until the age of two years.

The researchers conducted a study on the correct breastfeeding techniques. During breastfeeding, the patient appeared relaxed, but she was unable to detach the

baby's latch when her breast felt empty. The patient also allows the baby's head to be tilted back, not positioning the baby's head facing the breast. The baby also does not open his mouth wide and only sucks on the mother's nipple, causing it to become sore. The patient states that this sore nipple is due to the baby nursing too much. The patient mentions that she breastfeeds the baby on a schedule, which includes when the baby cries, after the baby bathes, when her breast milk feels abundant, and when the baby sticks out his tongue. The patient's breast milk production is quite abundant, but the patient has never stored her milk in breast milk bags and kept it in the freezer. The patient can properly burp her baby after breastfeeding.

The patient's experience with breastfeeding techniques for both of her previous children was the same as the breastfeeding technique for her third child at this time, which was before receiving education. However, the patient mentioned that there were no issues in the breastfeeding process other than sore nipples. Due to the close age gap between the second and third child, the patient feels comfortable breastfeeding.

Next, the assessment of the patient's knowledge regarding Exclusive Breastfeeding continued. The patient stated that they do not know much about the benefits of breast milk, mentioning that what matters is that the baby's nutritional needs are met. Then the researchers provided an initial questionnaire about mothers' knowledge of Exclusive Breastfeeding. The initial questionnaire score was 24 correct answers out of 30 checklist forms (knowledge increased), and the final questionnaire score was 26 correct answers. (knowledge has greatly increased).

3.3 Results of Knowledge on Breastfeeding Techniques and Exclusive Breastfeeding before Education is Provided.

While breastfeeding the baby, the patient appears relaxed during the feeding, but she cannot detach the baby's latch when her breast feels empty. The patient also allows the baby's head to be tilted back, not positioning the baby's head facing the breast. The baby also does not open its mouth wide, so the baby only sucks on the mother's nipple. The patient says she is breastfeeding her baby on a schedule. The patient said that the sore nipples were caused by the baby breastfeeding too much. The patient can properly burp her baby after breastfeeding.

The assessment of patients' knowledge regarding Exclusive Breastfeeding revealed that patients did not have a strong understanding of its benefits; they mentioned that what mattered most was ensuring the baby received adequate nutrition. Subsequently, the researcher provided an initial questionnaire about mothers' knowledge of Exclusive Breastfeeding. Following this, the patients were educated on the importance of Exclusive Breastfeeding for infants and taught the correct breastfeeding techniques. On the final day, the researcher administered a concluding questionnaire regarding mothers' knowledge of Exclusive Breastfeeding.

Table 1: mother's knowledge score

Result Table	Before	After
Score	24	26

In this table, it can be seen that the mothers' knowledge has significantly increased with an addition of 2 points.

Figure 1. Result Graphic

3.4 The results of knowledge about breastfeeding techniques and exclusive breastfeeding after education has been provided.

After educating the patients, their knowledge level regarding breastfeeding techniques and exclusive breastfeeding increased, namely: the baby's attachment to the mother improved, the mother's ability to position the baby correctly improved, the mother's breasts were empty after breastfeeding more often, and the baby's suckling improved. The mother's knowledge of exclusive breastfeeding significantly increased, with a final score of 26 out of 30.

3.5 Results of the Intervention obtained from the Literature Study

Based on the research (Fidayanti, 2023)⁹, the health education provided by the researcher resulted in changes in the level of knowledge and the ability of mothers to breastfeed properly and correctly. Education about breastfeeding is very important to achieve a positive breastfeeding experience, which can lead to changes in breastfeeding behavior. This education aims to achieve the goal of successful breastfeeding by addressing aspects such as providing information about breastfeeding and teaching the correct breastfeeding techniques.

In the Scientific Journal of Health Works (Rismayanti, 2021), it is stated that postpartum mothers' knowledge about breastfeeding techniques is greatly influenced by age, education, and previous experience. The increase in a mother's knowledge is due to the enhancement of her understanding after receiving health education, which encompasses the cognitive domain that influences an individual's actions (over behavior). This is in line with the theory of knowledge that encompasses the cognitive domain, namely: knowing (recalling material that has been previously learned) and understanding. (the ability to accurately explain known objects and correctly interpret material).

The comparison of the case study results with the author's case and the Scientific Journal of Health Works (Rismayanti, 2021) shows that there was an increase in the

average knowledge score before and after health education on breastfeeding techniques for postpartum mothers. The results of this study align with previous research that indicates a significant influence between the intervention group and the control group, allowing us to conclude that there is an effect of the demonstration method on breastfeeding technique skills in postpartum mothers. These findings are supported by earlier research showing a significant relationship between mothers' knowledge of proper breastfeeding techniques and the lactation issues that arise during the breastfeeding period.

In the results of the case study, the researchers concluded that the increase in mothers' knowledge about breastfeeding techniques and exclusive breastfeeding before and after education was significantly different. This is due to the lack of literacy among patients and limited exposure to information regarding postpartum mothers and breastfeeding.

4. CONCLUSIONS

There is an influence of education about breastfeeding techniques for postpartum mothers on mothers' knowledge about exclusive breast milk. This breastfeeding technique aims to maximize a mother's ability to breastfeed her baby exclusively with breast milk. Additionally, a mother's knowledge about exclusive breastfeeding can also influence her success in breastfeeding, ensuring that the baby receives proper nutrition. Education on breastfeeding techniques can enhance a mother's understanding of correct breastfeeding practices and increase her awareness of the importance of exclusive breastfeeding for the baby until the child reaches two years of age.

5. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

A heartfelt thank you is dedicated to my fellow lecturers at the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health in Pangkalpinang, the D3 nursing students of the Health Polytechnic of the Ministry of Health in Pangkalpinang, and to all the friends who cannot be mentioned one by one.

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